

Editorial

A new pathway is identified in the initiation and progression of eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) and its treatment strategies.

Information Objective

The purpose of the findings presented in to be bring an important finding on the role of NLRP3/Caspase1/IL-18 pathway involvement in the induction of food allergen-induced esophageal inflammatory disease termed as eosinophilic esophagitis to the attention of our readers and general public that has no assess to the published data presented not on public assess.

Commentary on the Currently published study

Eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) is a now well recognized global disease, prominent in pediatric population and the prevalence have been gradually increasing over the course of the last three decades.¹ The symptoms of esophageal dysfunction are a result of the disease, which is defined by a chronic inflammation and fibrosis of the epithelium and subepithelial esophageal tissues characterize that is strongly linked to food allergies and is characterized by progressive esophageal dysfunction that is localized to the esophagus and is dominated by eosinophils and associated with inflammatory or fibrotic blockages of the esophagus, which are present in most patients.² Notably, last more than 2 decades crucial roles were believed to be performed in the early stage and development stage of EoE by an abundance of inflammatory cytokines, which were believed to be mostly produced by Th2 cells, and by TGF β -mediated fibrosis and remodeling.³ This

type of immune response is associated with an abnormally high level of release of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, IL-33, and eotaxins-3. Multiple immune cell types, including mast cells, and IgE-producing B cells, can contribute to esophageal inflammation throughout the EoE process. However, still the pathophysiology of EoE is highly intricate and has not yet been fully understood.²

Yet, traditional methods of treating EoE have included dietary changes, proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), and oral topical corticosteroids (TCS). The medications, diet, and dilation are the treatments that are now available for EoE patients. The first medication specifically designed to address EoE was just recently given the green light to dispersible budesonide tablet in Europe. The monoclonal antibody dupilumab, which inhibits IL4/13 production, has just recently become available for the treatment of EoE in the United States dispersible budesonide tablet. Alterations to one's diet, as opposed to the use of pharmaceuticals, can be an effective treatment for EoE. There are numerous approaches, but they all share the common goal of minimizing exposure to certain food antigens. Finally, it's possible that (repetitive) endoscopic dilatation will continue to be the only therapy choice for patients who come with fibrostenotic illness. There have been discoveries of genetic variations in 13 putative EoE risk genes that

code for proteins. These genes include CAPN14, TSLP, and LRRC32, among others, which suggest that EoE genes are controlled by the EoE associated Th2 cytokines. Despite this, the outcomes of initial phase 3 clinical trials evaluating numerous different cytokine neutralizers, such as anti-IL-5, anti-IL-13, and anti-IL-4R α , have not yet provided satisfactory data in terms of treating EoE and improving patient's quality of life.⁴⁻⁶

In the recent issue on July 24, 2023 in Communication Biology-Nature (a journal from the Nature portfolio group, nature.com) from the laboratory of Prof. Anil Mishra of Medicine/Pulmonary Department and Eosinophilic Disorder Center of Tulane University School of Medicine (New Orleans, LA) group of investigators published a study on the initiation, progression and treatment of EoE. The research team implicated NLRP3/Caspase1/IL-18 pathway in the initiation and progression of EoE disease and provided the evidences that by inhibiting this pathway by respective inhibitors disease improve in food and allergen-induced experimental EoE.⁷ The research was funded in part by NIH's National Institute of Allergy and infectious Diseases (NIAID). To investigate the significance of NLRP3/Caspase1/IL-18 pathway, the first showed the evidences that these molecules are induce in both experimental and human EoE following allergen exposure. They provided evidences that even in IL-5 overexpressed mice do **not** show EoE characteristics; but if you inject rIL-18 to these mice most EoE characteristics in mice are visible like highly induced intraepithelial cells, eosinophils degranulation, basal cell proliferation and highly induced collagen deposition in the epithelial mucosa. In addition, the study provided most

critical evidence on the role of IL-18 in EoE induction by intravenously injecting rIL-18 to GATA1-deficient (Δ dblGATA) mice. Of note, Δ dblGATA mice are completely deficient in eosinophils and following only 3 injection of rIL-18 for one-week and mice showed highly induced most of the pathological characteristics of EoE.⁷ These findings indicate an important role of IL-18 in the initiation of EoE pathogenesis, including intraepithelial eosinophilia, indicating a critical role of antigen-presenting cells and epithelial cells are responsible for the production of NLRP3 regulated IL-18, not Th2 cells or eosinophils responsive chemokines eotaxin-1, -2, -3 in the induction of EoE. The rationale that Th2 cells or eotaxins are not critical in initiating the EoE, based on our early reports that naïve esophagus has highly induced baseline eotaxin gene, but esophagus is devoid of eosinophils. In addition, we also reported that CD4⁺, CD8⁺ T cells-deficient and eotaxin-deficient mice, including RAG1 mice are not protected from the induction of allergen-induced EoE.⁸ Furthermore, eotaxin-3 is not detected in mice, but still accumulate eosinophils in epithelial mucosa following the injection of rIL-18, provide concerns on the role of even eotaxin-3 in EoE pathogenesis. IL-18 is a member of the IL-1 family of cytokines and an IFN- γ -inducing factor. Earlier, the same Laboratory of Dr. Mishra reported that IL-18 had the ability to both generate an IL-5-independent subgroup of CD274-expressed pathogenic eosinophils and transform IL-5-generated naive eosinophils into CD274⁺ pathogenic eosinophils.⁹ Furthermore, the investigators provided evidences that NLRP3, inhibitors N-[(1,2,3,5,6,7-hexahydro-s-indacen-4-yl) amino] carbonyl]-4-(1-hydroxy-1-methylethyl)-2-furansulfonamide (MCC950), -hydroxybutyrate (BHB), the caspase-1 inhibitor Belnacasan (VX-765)

and neutralizing IL-18 are the promising therapeutic targets for EoE. NLRP3 inhibiting compounds such as N-[(1,2,3,5,6,7-hexahydro-s-indacen-4-yl) amino] carbonyl]-4-(1-hydroxy-1-

Summarized study by concluding figure.

Western blot analysis indicates that blocking of NLRP3 normalize inflammatory pathway, which is indicated by details shown in schematic diagram.

well-characterized inhibitors now available, including humanized neutralizing-IL-18 with some pharmaceutical companies.⁷ Therefore, the investigators proposed a double-blind clinical trial is under their protected international filled patent application. The investigators indicated that these proposed inhibitors clinical trials would protect IL-5 generated naïve eosinophils, a most important cell types home prenatally and needed for the development and in the maintenance of innate immunity in health and deplete only IL-18 generated and transformed pathogenic eosinophils.¹⁰

methylethyl)-2-furansulfonamide (MCC950), hydroxybutyrate (BHB), and the caspase-1 inhibitor Belnacasan (VX-765) are the most selective and

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References

1. Mishra A. Mechanism of eosinophilic esophagitis. Immunol Allergy Clin North Am 2009; 29:29-40.
2. Zaidi AK, Mussarat A, Mishra A. Diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for eosinophilic esophagitis. Clin Pract (Lond) 2014; 11:351-67.
3. Mishra A, Wang M, Pemmaraju VR, Collins MH, Fulkerson PC, Abonia JP, et al. Esophageal Remodeling Develops as a Consequence of Tissue

Specific IL-5-Induced Eosinophilia.

Gastroenterology 2008; 134:204-14.

4. Gomez Torrijos E, Gonzalez-Mendiola R, Alvarado M, Avila R, Prieto-Garcia A, Valbuena T, et al. Eosinophilic Esophagitis: Review and Update. *Front Med (Lausanne)* 2018; 5:247.
5. Lucendo AJ, Lopez-Sanchez P. Targeted Therapies for Eosinophilic Gastrointestinal Disorders. *BioDrugs* 2020; 34:477-93.
6. Lucendo AJ. Pharmacological treatments for eosinophilic esophagitis: current options and emerging therapies. *Expert Rev Clin Immunol* 2020; 16:63-77.
7. Yadavalli CS, Upparahalli Venkateshaiah S, Kumar S, Kandikattu HK, Oruganti L, Kathera CS, et al. Allergen-induced NLRP3/caspase1/IL-18 signaling initiate eosinophilic esophagitis and respective inhibitors protect disease pathogenesis. *Commun Biol* 2023; 6:763.
8. Mishra A, Schlotman J, Wang M, Rothenberg ME. Critical role for adaptive T cell immunity in experimental eosinophilic esophagitis in mice. *J Leukoc Biol* 2007; 81:916-24.
9. Venkateshaiah SU, Mishra A, Manohar M, Verma AK, Rajavelu P, Niranjan R, et al. A critical role of IL-18 in transformation and maturation of naive eosinophils to pathogenic eosinophils. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2018.
10. Mishra A, Hogan SP, Lee JJ, Foster PS, Rothenberg ME. Fundamental signals that regulate eosinophil homing to the gastrointestinal tract. *J Clin Invest* 1999; 103:1719-27.